

Current methods of Yoga for refining the Human values in physical education and sports: a study

Dr. Vishwanth A. Kodape

Director of Physical Education, Science College, Pauni, Dist. Bhandara

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ABSTRACT

Classic yoga takes you through a beginners course in which the exercise are very gentle, slow and easy to follow, as you learn to move and breathe in a new way. Once you are comfortable with these you can move on the intermediate and advanced asanas, which will demand greater levels of stamina and suppleness to perform. "Yoga is mirror, to look at ourselves from within."

Keywords: Rawanwadi, Avifauna Diversity

Introduction

The practice of yoga was common in ancient India where aisonething and Maharishis practical yoga for the control of mind and body. The origin of yoga can be traced from Hindu civilization in Vedas. It was mentioned that yoga was considered good for health fitness and well being. Aryans did yogic exercise in 3000 B.C. yoga aims at the development of perfect coordination between mind and body. Most of the sacred writing of India like Vedas, Upanishads, Puranas and Tantras have we explained yoga to achieve highest degree of knowledge.

Meaning of Yoga: The word yoga has been derived from the Sanskrit word "Yug" which means to join individual some with soul of divine. It is a comprehensive, system linking body, breath, mind. Intelligence, wisdom and sprit, yoga helps in aerating balance and harmony in body. Yoga also teaches to balance the mental urge to push, control and be assertive with the impulse to yield, submit and be passive. Pranayama is considered as the science of breath became the body gets energy through respiratory system. The other systems of the body are also directly related with

prana. Pranayama this refers to extension of breath and its control, one humans absorb prana (Breath) through fresh air in three ways,

- Normal Breath
- Deep Breath
- Yogic Breath

Thus yoga helps in attaining a balanced attitudinal equilibrium.

Definition of Yoga:

According to Patanjali- Patanjali being the founder of yoga, according to him yoga is to stabilize the mind for the union of atma and paramatma. He further simply defined it as yoga is a way to join God. Elements of Yoga- The elements of yoga have been described as Astanga yoga. The Astanga yoga have been derived from two words i.e. Ashta which means eight and anga means Limbs, According to Patanjali path of internal purifications for revealing the universal self consist of the eight spiritual practices given below.

- Yama (moral code)
- Niyama (self purification and study)
- Asana (posture)
- Pranayama (Breath control)
- Pratyahara (sense control)
- Dharana (concentration)
- Dhyana (meditation)
- Samadhi (contemplation)

Astanga Yoga:

Yoga is also known as Astanga yoga, Astanga means "8 limbs" or "steps" and is divided into 3 disciplines. The disciplines bahirangasadhana, comprises ethical practices in the form of yama, or general ethical principles, niyama, or self-restraint, and physical practice in the form of asanas as well as pranayama. The second discipline, antaranga-sadhana, is emotional or mental discipline brought to maturity by pranayama and pratyahara, or mental detachment, lastly, antaratma-sadhana is the successful quest of the soul through dharma, dhana and Samadhi.

Harmony of Body and Mind:

Asanas cater to the needs of each individual according to his or her specific constitution and physical condition. They involve vertical, horizontal and cycling

movements, which provide energy to the system by directing the blood supply to the areas of the body which need it most. In yoga, each cell is observed, attended to and provided with a fresh supply of blood, allowing it to function smoothly. The mind is naturally active and dynamic, which the soul is luminous. The practice of yoga stimulates and changes emotional attitudes, converting apprehensiveness into courage, in decision and poor judgment into positive decision making skills, and emotional instability confidence and mental equilibrium.

Yoga and Physical Fitness:

Most types of exercise are competitive, yoga, although non-competitive is nevertheless challenging. The challenges to one's own will power, it is a competition one's self and one's body. Exercise usually involves quick and forceful body movements. It has repeated action which often leads to exertion, tension and fatigue, yoga asanas, on the other hand, involve movements which bring stability to the body, the sense, the mind, the intellect, the consciousness and finally, to the conscience. The very essence of an asana is steady movements, a process that does not simply but finds fulfillment in tranquility.

Stimulative Exercise:-

Yoga asanas are stimulative exercise, while other endurance exercises are irritative for instance, medical sports claim that jogging stimulates heart. In fact, though the heart rate of the jogger increases, the heart is not stimulated in the yogic sense of being energized and invigorated. In yoga, back bend, for example, is more physically demanding than jogging, but the heart rate is steady, rhythmic pace. Asanas do not lead to breathlessness when practicing yoga, strength and power play separate roles to achieve a perfect balance in every part of the body, as well as the mind. After such stimulating exercise a sense of rejuvenation and a fresh surge of energy follow.

Other Benefit of yoga

Holistic Yoga: A fitness Mantra.

One can be said to be in a perfect state of health when one is physically fit, mentally calm and emotionally steady," says Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, Beyond just physical fitness, yoga strengthens mental and emotional

capacity. A yoga practice inspired by family fitness goals growing up with a father who was a sports enthusiast, I used to tag along with him on the tennis court. My father would often bring home trophies after winning tournaments in Basketball, Tennis and bowling. While I did not become a professional Tennis player as my dad secretly wished. I eagerly shared his goal of achieving fitness for me, this meant playing sports, joining dance lessons and learning yoga and meditation to boost my energy levels.

Yoga and the body-breath-mind link.

Have you ever noticed the breath while inhaling the scent of a flower, on a recent walk in Paris, just at the brink of spring, I noticed the blooming flowers spilling over garden gates. Happily breathing in the scent of roses and daffodils, I observed my breath. I was taking in long, deep inhalations my body was invigorated with energy or that vital life force called prana I felt strong, alert and joyful, fit to tackle whatever might come my way. A person could tolerate going without sleep or food a few days and still remain alive. Yet how long could one go without breathing? Yoga and breathing are linked with attention on the breath and practicing breathing exercises to boost lung capacity, yoga practice keeps the energy level high when the body has high level of prana, the mind is clear and happy.

Glide into Meditation:-

Now the body is stable, the mind clear of thoughts the stage is set to slip into meditation effortlessly. By this, we mean that just like we can't force ourselves to sleep until it happens on its own, even meditation cannot be forced or done with effort. It just happens and simply glide through it. And it's not just the experience during meditation that matters but how you feel after. The mind becomes quieter and unperturbed, and you find yourself much more in control of things. All these practices combined together can help switch the mind from a state of turbulence to the bliss of tranquility. The mind doesn't shut off but it does stop chattering, letting you be 100 percent in the moment and enjoying it completely.

Conclusion

Sports are highly demanding and competitive and yoga moves in the opposite direction with its comp apparent emphasis on a relaxed approach and detached state of mind. However, the state of mind and physical preparedness that yoga brings is exactly the same state the most successful players speak of when at the peak of their performance. Who cannot perform at his best while being relaxed, ready and confident? And who can't gracefully accept victory or defeat if his body, mind and spirit has the equanimity of a yogi? Fill in the form below to learn more about how yoga can aid you in overcoming issues naturally with minimum lifestyle changes.

Conflicts of interest: The authors stated that no conflicts of interest.

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